

Abstract

Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) and substance use: Findings from a national data among adolescents in the United States

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Background: Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) and substance use disorder (SUD) are major public health problems in the US. The goals of this study were: 1) to explore the association between ACEs and SUD; and 2) to identify the role of resilience factors for SUD among US adolescents with ACEs. *Methods:* We utilized four-year data (2016-2019) from the National Survey on Children Health (NSCH), a nationally representative cross-sectional survey (aged 12-17; $N=53,828$). ACEs, child resilience, and family resilience were continuous variables. Clinician-reported SUD was dichotomized into “yes” or “no.” Multivariate logistic regression was conducted to analyze the main effects of ACEs and SUD and the interaction effects of resilience factors on SUD. *Results:* The study sample comprised of 51% males, 51% Non-Hispanic Whites, 25% Hispanics, and 14% African Americans. Adolescents with one ACE had about three times higher odds of being diagnosed with SUD (aOR=2.74; 95%CI: 1.77–4.24, $p<.001$); the odds of an SUD diagnosis was six times greater for those with 2-3 ACEs (aOR=6.22; 95%CI: 4.19–9.24, $p<.001$), and 20 times higher for respondents with ≥ 4 ACEs (aOR=20.32; 95%CI:13.63–30.31, $p<.001$). For adolescents without ACEs, each unit increase in child resilience, the odds of SUD decreased by 49% ($b[SE]= -0.67[0.08]$, $p<.001$) for each unit increase in family resilience and the odds of SUD decreased by 29% ($b[SE]= -0.33[0.07]$, $p<.001$). *Conclusion:* ACEs are a major risk for developing SUD among US adolescents. Evidence-based interventions should be provided for adolescents with ACEs to mitigate future SUD and to enhance child and family resilience as protective factors.

Program planning Public health or related research Social and behavioral sciences

